

Study of Efficacy of Ropivacaine Alone Versus Ropivacaine with Dexamethasone in Clavicular Branchial Plexus Block in Andhra Pradesh Population

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Received: 25-09-2024 / Revised: 23-10-2024 / Accepted: 26-11-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: An anesthetic drug without cardiotoxicity, a long-acting regional anesthetic structurally related to bupivacaine, is ropivacaine. The efficacy of ropivacaine alone and in combination with 8 mg dexamethasone is compared to evaluate the efficacy of both local anesthetics.

Method: Out of 90 (ninety), 45 patients were given Dexamethasone and Ropivacaine, and 45 patients were given Ropivacaine alone.

Results: The onset of motor block and sensory block duration of motor block were longer in patients treated with dexamethasone and Ropivacaine with a significant p-value ($p < 0.001$) as compared to ropivacaine alone.

Conclusion: In the present pragmatic comparative study. It is confirmed and concluded that dexamethasone added to ropivacaine in a supraclavicular block for upper limb surgery significantly shortens the onset time and prolongs the duration of sensory and motor block without causing any sedation or toxicity.

Keywords: Dexamethasone, Ropivacaine, sensory block, motor block, brachial plexus.

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Introduction

Brachial plexus block is often used either as an adjuvant to general anesthesia (GA) or as a sole anesthesia modality. Brachial plexus blockage for ambulatory upper limb surgery can significantly reduce pain and nausea, allowing for faster discharge from the hospital when compared with GA [1] and is equally useful in patients with significant comorbidity.

Various anaesthetics alone or in combination with different durations of post-operative analgesia for a long time have met with limited success [2]. Bupivacaine is a well-established long-acting regional anesthetic. Like all amide anesthetics, it has been associated with cardiotoxicity when used in high concentrations or when accidentally administered intravascularly.

Hence there is a need for a drug that can have all the advantages of bupivacaine with its cardiotoxicity. Ropivacaine is a long-acting regional anesthetic that is structurally related to bupivacaine. It is an S (-) enantiomer, unlike bupivacaine, which is a racemate, developed for the purpose of reducing potential cardiotoxicity and improving relative sensory and motor block profiles [3].

It is also studied that, Dexamethasone (50 mcg) added to perieural local anaesthetic injection augment the duration of peripheral nerve block analgesia hence an attempt is made to compare ropivacaine alone versus ropivacaine and dexamethasone in supra-clavicular brachial plexus block and the results were evaluated and compared [4].

Material and Method

90 (ninety) patients were admitted to the surgery department of the Nimra Institute of Medical Sciences (NIMS) in Jupidi, Ibrahim Patnam, Vijaywada, Krishna District-521456, Andhra Pradesh, were studied.

Inclusion Criteria: The patients aged 10-60 years posted for various elective upper limb surgeries. ASA Grade I and II were selected for study.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients below 18 years ASA grade III, IV, or Vth patients using tricyclic antidepressants, pregabalin, serotonin-norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors, or tramadol. Patients hypersensitive to amide local anesthesia or with a history of hypersensitivity to dexamethasone were excluded from the study.

Method:

Every patient underwent a routine examination for the general condition of the patient. Height, weight, and age of the patients were noted. Pre-anesthetic evaluation was done in the evening before surgery in all patients. A detailed examination of the cardiovascular and respiratory systems was done. Moreover, surface anatomy where the block was going to be given. Blood was collected for routine examination, each as Hb%, CBC, fasting, and postprandial blood sugars. Blood urea and S. creatinine levels. ECG, and chest X-ray was taken.

Urine examination for albumin, sugar, and microscopy was also done in every patient. Out of 60 patients, 30 patients are given Ropivacaine alone and are named as the R group, and 30 are given Ropivacaine and Dexamethasone and are named as the RD group. The patients in the group R are administered 28 ml of 0.5% Ropivacaine injection alone + 2 ml saline, and RD was given 28 ml of 0.5% Ropivacaine with 2 ml of 8 mg Dexamethasone.

Every patient was premedicated with IV 1 mg midazolam 20 minutes before giving the block. The patients were connected with a monitor to record heart rate (HR), non-invasive measurement of systolic blood pressure (SBP), diastolic blood pressure (DBP), continuous electrocardiogram (ECG), monitoring, and hemoglobin oxygen saturation (SPO₂). The baseline systolic BP, DBP, and SBP were recorded. The site at injection was shaved and disinfected. The injection site was infiltrated with 1 ml of 2% lidocaine subcutaneously. A nerve stimulator was used to locate the brachial plexus. The location endpoint was a distal motor response with an output lower than 0.6 ml. During injection, negative aspiration was performed after 6.5-7.0 ml to avoid intravascular injection.

Sensory and motor block along with monitoring of vitals was determined every 5 minutes in the first 30 minutes and then every 15 minutes during 1st hour, followed by every second hour for 24 hours. Any hypertensive reaction to the drugs, evidence of pneumothorax, and adverse events were also monitored. To evaluate duration sensory block and motor block, patients were asked to inform the time when incisional discomfort as a sensation of pain began and also the time when full power returned to the shoulder. In the postoperative period, when

the patients complained of pain at the operative site, injection Diclofenac 75 mg IM was given, and patients were followed up for 24 hours for any side effects.

Duration of study was from September 2023 to October 2024.

Statistical Analysis:

The demographic profile and duration of surgery in both groups were compared with a z-test and results were noted. The statistical analysis was carried out using SPSS software. The ratio of male and female was 2:1.

Observation and Results

Table 1: Demographic profile of comparison in both groups

- Age (years) was 37.33 (\pm 10.5) in group R and 35.42 (\pm 8.60) in the RD group, t-test 0.94 and $p > 0.34$ (p-value was insignificant).
- Weight (in kg) was 157.8 (\pm 6.15) in group R and 158.9 (\pm 3.70) in the RD group, t-test 1.02 and $p > 0.03$ (p-value was insignificant).

Table 2: Comparison of surgical parameters in both groups

- Duration of surgery (minutes): 102.60 (\pm 30.10) in group R, 101.02 (\pm 34.2) in the RD group; t-test was 0.23, and $p > 0.81$ (p-value is not significant).
- Onset of surgery (minutes): 16.14 (\pm 1.58) in group R, 16.14 (\pm 2.50) in the RD group; t-test was 0.00, and $p > 0.001$ (p-value is insignificant).
- Onset of motor block (in minutes): 14.93 (\pm 2.70) in group R, 18.68 (\pm 2.72) in the RD group; t-test was 6.56, and $p < 0.001$.
- Duration of sensory block (in minutes): 509.80 (\pm 31.05) in group R, 1012.68 (\pm 24.8) in the RD group; t-test was 84.8, and $p < 0.001$ (p-value is highly significant).
- Duration of motor block (in minutes): 456.48 (\pm 26.40) in group R, 863.04 (\pm 26.90) in the RD group; t-test was 72.3, and $p < 0.001$ (p-value is highly significant).
- Total number of rescue injections in 24 hours: 2.74 (\pm 0.48) in group R, 1.38 (\pm 0.46) in the RD group; t-test was 13.7, and $p < 0.001$ (p-value is highly significant).

Table 1: Comparison of Demographic profile of patients in both groups

Parameters	Group R (45) Mean \pm SD	Group RD (45) Mean \pm SD	t test	p value
Age (in years)	37.33 (\pm 10.5)	35.42 (\pm 8.60)	0.94	$p > 0.34$
Weight (in Kg)	157.8 (\pm 6.15)	158.9 (\pm 3.70)	1.02	$p > 0.30$

Figure 1: Comparison of Demographic profile of patients in both groups

Table 2: Comparison of surgical parameters in both groups

Parameters	Group R (45) Mean ±SD	Group RD (45) Mean ±SD	t test	p value
Duration of surgery (min)	102.60 (± 30.10)	101.02 (± 34.2)	0.23	p>0.81
Onset of surgery (in min)	161.4 (±1.58)	16.14 (± 2.50)	0.00	p>0.01
Onset of motor lock (in Min)	14.93 (± 2.70)	18.68 (± 2.70)	6.56	P<0.001
Duration of sensory Block (in Min)	509.80 (± 31.05)	1012.68 (± 24.8)	84.8	P<0.001
Duration of Motor Block (in Min)	456.48 (± 26.40)	863.04 (±26.90)	72.3	P<0.001
Total No. of rescue injection in 24 hours	2.74 (± 0.48)	1.38 (± 0.46)	13.7	P<0.001

Figure 2: Comparison of surgical parameters in both groups

Discussion

In the present study of the efficacy of Ropivacaine alone versus Ropivacaine with dexamethasone in a supraclavicular brachial plexus block. In the comparison of the demographic profile of patients, age (in years) and weight (kg) were compared in both the R group and the RD group; the p-value was insignificant (>0.34) (Table 1). The onset of motor block (in minutes), duration of sensory block (in minutes), duration of motor block (in minutes) the total number of rescue injections in 24 hours had significant ($p < 0.001$) results. These findings are more or less in agreement with previous studies [5,6,7].

Dexamethasone is known for its anti-inflammatory, immunosuppressive, and antiemetic properties; these corticosteroids exert their effects by inhibition of phospholipase A-2 as well as changes in cell function induced by glucocorticoid receptor activation [8].

The mechanism involved for the extended analgesic effect of dexamethasone is attributed to its action locally on nociceptive c-fibers (via glucocorticoid receptors) to increase the activity of inhibitory potassium channels, thus decreasing their activity [9]. It is reported that dexamethasone effectively prolonged duration of analgesia, which is mediated via the glucocorticoid receptor. When dexamethasone alone is used in a regional block, the blockade does not occur [10]. Dexamethasone is proposed to bring about this effect by altering the function of potassium channels in excitable cells [11]. Hence, dexamethasone must be added with another anesthetic drug to enhance its duration of motor or sensory blockage.

Summary and Conclusion

The present study has proved that dexamethasone and ropivacaine used for supraclavicular brachial plexus block for upper limb surgery have significantly shortened the onset time and prolonged the duration of motor and sensory block without producing sedation in patients and without any side effects like nausea and vomiting. This study demands further such studies in a large number of patients in both sexes at different age groups to confirm these results because the exact mechanism and actions of the Dexamethasone and Ropicaine combination are still unclear.

Limitation of study: Owing to tertiary location, small number of patients, and lack of the latest techniques, we have limited findings and results.

This research work was approved by the ethical committee of the Nimra Institute of Medical Sciences (NIMS), Jupidi, Ibrahim Patnam, Vijaywada, Krishna District-521456, and Andhra Pradesh.

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